

Managing Editor's Column

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Here is another “regular” issue of J.UCS with seven interesting papers coming from (in alphabetical order) Germany, Malaysia, South Africa, Spain and USA, with authors from Spain dominating this time! As in many regular issues before, also the articles in this issue deal with a wide range of topics in computer science, once again witnessing to the ‘universality’ of J.UCS.

I trust you will find some of the papers fitting your taste.

Let me take this opportunity to thank all reviewers who were involved in the review process of the published papers for their support and valuable comments which helped to improve the papers.

Finally, I encourage not only young researchers and students to submit high-quality articles to J.UCS, but also the members of our editorial board! Good submissions are a prerequisite for good publications and good publications are essential for a good rating of the journal which again, is decisive for securing its future. Thanks for your support and enjoy the issue!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

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